

Test and develop a method for the implementation of silvopastoral mosaics, using remote sensing approaches, that supports agricultural and forestry activity in areas of Pyrenean oak, which typically have low agricultural value

Introduction

The OG SILVPAST evaluated the use of livestock grazing in two pilot areas to assess the contribution for assisting in forest regeneration (by aiding in processes like thinning and biomass regulation for preventing fires), employed genetic analyses to evaluate forest diversity and provide insights for restoration initiatives, and experimented remote sensing techniques for monitoring purposes.

Results

The existence of parcels with different uses and management objectives in a silvopastoral mosaic is advantageous for landscape sustainability by promoting synergies among the different parcels, diversifying the uses, and mitigating potential impacts. These synergies have been identified in the pilot areas of SILVPAST.

- At Quinta da França (pilot area 1), the pastoral use of the regenerating forest was supported by the neighbouring pastures, which provided the necessary food for the animals and allowed for maintaining a sufficiently high stocking rate to achieve effects on the regulation of vegetation structure and on the growth of understory shrubs in the oak forest. On the other hand, no significant effects were identified on the understory plant species richness (i.e., no promotion or impoverishment of biodiversity was observed). However, this result requires further future evaluation as it pertains to short-term effects. Moderate impacts on the recruitment of young oaks were also identified, highlighting the need to maintain exclusion areas that provide the necessary conditions for natural regeneration to occur. Furthermore, genetic studies identified a good proportion of seed regeneration and suggested the existence of large-scale genetic exchanges, which favour the genetic diversity of the forest. Finally, satellite image analysis suggests that

the pastoral use of the forest provides benefits to the natural pastures in the clearings, with an anticipation of the growing season and increased productivity (compared to the control parcel). Possibly, this effect was promoted by the lower amount of senescent herbaceous biomass accumulated in the autumn (due to previous grazing), which improved conditions for seed germination and seedling emergence in early autumn, including more sunlight and space.

- In the Médio Côa (pilot area 2), a complementarity in species composition was identified among different land uses (i.e., with species communities associated to each use), which enhances landscape-scale biodiversity. Grazing by semi-wild horses with low stocking rates did not result in significant differences in vegetation structure and shrub cover volume compared to the non-grazed area. However, differences were found in the coverage of tall herbs, which was lower in the parcel with horses. These results suggest the potential of this grazing regime, but also the need for additional management measures, such as shrub clearing to create open areas (which will then be maintained through grazing), in order to improve performance in terms of biomass regulation and fire prevention. Lastly, the recruitment level of young oaks was lower in the pasture parcel with cattle, which reinforces the need to maintain exclusion areas or areas with lower stocking rates, and if necessary, implement local measures for the protection of regeneration."

Lessons learned

Livestock grazing at moderate densities helped to regulate shrub biomass and tall grasses and to create vertical discontinuities; however, these densities required the combined use of pastures, adjacent to the forest, to ensure adequate food resources and water points (if not available in the forest).

Despite the use of GPS collars, there were signal failures, and animal injuries not attended in the due time. Hence, improved approaches are needed to effectively monitor livestock in a free-ranging regime in complex forest environments.

Initial monitoring data indicates that the impact on biodiversity is neutral when compared to non-grazed areas.

Grazing reduced levels of senescent herbs, which accumulated between growing seasons, and facilitated more vigorous grow in the autumn.

Tree recruitment was moderately impacted, which is of low concern given the abundant recruitment at the pilot sites, but highlights the need for protective measures in areas with limited recruitment.

Genetic studies identified a good proportion of seed regeneration and suggested the existence of large-scale genetic exchanges, which favour the genetic diversity."

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Figure 6. Distribution of sampled Pyrenean oaks in Quinta da França (A) and Médio Côa (B). The trees with a clone in the vicinity are marked in red.

Figure 7. Distribution of Pyrenean oaks in the sub-population (30m x 30m) in Quinta da França (A) and Médio Côa (B). The trees with a clone in the vicinity are marked in red.

Figure 1. Upper photo, distribution of the studied trees. On the left, the Pyrenean oaks from Quinta da França, and on the right the trees from Médio Côa. Trees with a clone in the vicinity are marked in red.

Bottom photo, the same distribution showing specific sub-populations of oaks.

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://www.terraprima.pt/pt/projecto/23>

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